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CONFLICT OF INTEREST IN JOURNALISTIC ACTIVITY

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The process of documenting in journalistic activity not always can be characterized as easy or very easy. It is almost every time confronted with difficult researches, misunderstanding, disagreements or even conflicts. These facts make more difficult the documentation process and, ultimately, the realization of a journalistic material which purpose is to inform the public about topics of great interest. These situations of unequivocal and unsafe interpretation sometimes generate a critical attitude towards media activity among the public, with obvious consequences: lack of credibility of the press, suspicions of partisanship, ironic attitude towards the press, etc. The article below tries to reveal all the characteristics of conflict of interests in journalistic activity and possibilities to avoid it and to keep the profession's image on the corresponding level of ethics.

Keywords: conflict of interests, ethics, public interest, transparency, promoting, individual responsibility, civil society, organizational culture.

CONFLICTUL DE INTERESE ÎN ACTIVITATEA JURNALISTICĂ

Multiplele relații pe care le stabilesc jurnaliștii în activitatea lor cotidiană nu sunt întotdeauna lipsite de pericolul neînțelegerilor, conflictelor, dezacordurilor, inclusiv cu sursele informaționale, iar acest fapt îngreunează mult procesul de documentare și de realizare a unui material jurnalistic menit să informeze publicul despre subiecte de larg interes. Prezența factorului uman în activitatea presei poate conduce la apariția unor situații când interesele celor care relaționează nu pot fi considerate tocmai congruente, astfel stabilindu-se anumite situații în care cei care interacționează vor fi nevoiți să aleagă ceva în detrimentul altcuiva. Tocmai aceste situații neclare, lipsite de interpretare sigură, generează uneori în rândul publicului o atitudine critică în adresa activității media, cu consecințe evidente: lipsă de credibilitate a presei, bănuiele de partizanat, atitudine ironică față de presă etc. Acest amalgam de situații și atitudini neunivoce, nu tocmai corespunzătoare unei activități jurnaliste transparente a condus la studierea fenomenului conflictului de interese în activitatea jurnalistică, fenomen, de altfel, prezent și în cadrul altor domenii de activitate umană, din perspectiva abordărilor deontologice. Articolul dat își propune să dezvăluie caracteristicile conflictului de interese în activitatea jurnalistică, aspectele care vizează legislația și etica în raport cu acest fenomen și propune recomandări pentru evitarea situațiilor de acest gen.

Cuvinte-cheie: conflict de interese, etică, interes public, transparență, promovare, responsabilitate individuală, societate civilă, cultură organizațională.

CONFLIT D'INTÉRÊTS DANS L'ACTIVITÉ JOURNALISTIQUE

Le processus de documentation dans l'activité journalistique ne peut pas toujours être caractérisé comme facile ou très facile. Il est presque à chaque fois confronté à des recherches difficiles, des malentendus, des désaccords ou même des conflits. Ces faits rendent plus difficile le processus de documentation et, en fin de compte, la réalisation d'un matériel journalistique dont le but est d'informer le public sur des sujets d'un grand intérêt. Ces situations d'interprétation non équivoque et dangereuse génèrent parfois une attitude critique envers l'activité des médias auprès du public, avec des conséquences évidentes: manque de crédibilité de la presse, soupçons de partisanerie, attitude ironique envers la presse, etc. L'article ci-dessous tente de révéler toutes les caractéristiques du conflit d'intérêts dans l'activité journalistique et les possibilités de l'éviter et de garder l'image de la profession sur le niveau d'éthique correspondant.

Mots-clés: *conflit d'intérêts, éthique, intérêt public, transparence, promotion, responsabilité individuelle, société civile, culture organisationnelle.*

КОНФЛИКТ ИНТЕРЕСОВ В ЖУРНАЛИСТСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Многочисленные отношения, которые журналисты устанавливают в своей повседневной работе, не всегда свободны от опасности недопонимания, конфликтов интересов, разногласий, в том числе с источниками информации и это делает процесс документирования и создания журналистского материала, предназначенного для информирования общественности, представляющим большой интерес. Логическое присутствие человеческого фактора в деятельности прессы неизбежно может привести к ситуациям, когда интересы тех, кто взаимосвязан, не могут абсолютно совпадать, что создает определенные ситуации, в которых взаимодействующим лицам придется что-либо выбирать в ущерб другим. Именно эти ситуации двусмысленности, не имея под собой надежного и обоснованного толкования, порой вызывают у общественности критическое отношение к деятельности СМИ, с очевидными последствиями: отсутствие доверия к прессе, подозрения в пристрастности, ироничное отношение к прессе, и так далее. Эти неоднозначные ситуации, не совсем соответствующие нормам прозрачности журналистской деятельности, приводят к необходимости изучения феномена конфликта интересов в журналистской работе, явления, присутствующего и в других сферах человеческой деятельности, с точки зрения норм деонтологии. Цель данной статьи - раскрыть суть конфликта интересов в журналистской деятельности, а также вопросов, связанных с законодательством и этикой в связи с этим явлением и разработка рекомендаций по предотвращению подобных ситуаций.

Ключевые слова: *конфликт интересов, этика, общественные интересы, прозрачность, продвижение, индивидуальная ответственность, гражданское общество, организационная культура.*

The multiple relationships that journalists daily establish in their daily activities are not always protected from the danger of misunderstandings, conflicts, disagreements, including, with information sources. This fact makes more difficult the process of documenting and, finally, writing a journalistic material which purpose is to inform the public about topics of great interest. The logical presence of the human factor in the press' activity can inevitably lead to situations when the interests of those who interact cannot be considered as congruent, thus establishing certain situ-

ations in which those who interact will have to choose something to detriment of someone or something else. Precisely, these situations of equivocation sometimes generate a critical attitude among the public towards the media activity, with obvious consequences: lack of credibility to the press, suspicion of partisanship, ironic attitude towards the press, etc. This amalgam of ambiguous situations and attitudes that don't exactly correspond to a transparent journalistic activity, led to the study of the conflict of interest phenomenon in journalistic activity, a phenomenon that is also present

in other fields of human activity, from the perspective of approaches, deontology definitions, etc.

The researcher R.Radu thinks that the definition of the conflict of interests cannot be fixed exactly [1, p.178], because the field of communication, with its basic actors, is one in a continuous change, flexible and which can't set boundaries between right and wrong activities. In this sense, the author considers more appropriate the use of the terms «deontological» and «non-deontological» each time when establishing the correspondence of the decisions taken by journalists in their daily activity related to the reflection of events of public interest. It is always easier to determine whether a behavior is deontological or not, if we refer it to certain professional norms. The practical written guide *Conflict of Interests in Journalistic Activity*, elaborated by the Moldovan Press Council, refers to the Law 16/2008 about the conflict of interests and defines it as a conflict between exercising the duties of the position held and the people's personal interests (...), in their capacity as private persons, which could inappropriately influence the objective and impartial fulfillment of their obligations and responsibilities under the law [2].

The law connects the notion of conflict of interests with the exercise of the public function (dignitaries, heads of administrative authorities, in the field of public health and education, public officials, etc.). Under these stipulations, we note that journalists, as it is, are not covered by this law. At the same time, we are aware that the responsibility towards the general public, but also to the editorial structure of which journalists belong, forces them to adopt an ethical behavior that would positively influence the credibility of the information transmitted and of the media activity as a whole. It should be noted that most definitions of conflict of interest do not explicitly include references to the activity of the media, but only to the activity of public officials. We can only deduce that journalists are indirectly targeted, because

of their activity in the public interest. According to Susan Rose-Ackerman's study, conflict of interest arises when "a person mixes its roles" [3, p.4], the author emphasizing the importance of identifying a clear dividing line between different types of roles the journalists could take on in their daily practice.

The Transparency International organization identifies the conflict of interest in the journalistic activity and defines it as a situation in which a person or entity for whom this person works, whether it is a government, a business, a press institute or an organization, civil society, has to choose between the duties and obligations related to its position, on the one hand, and its private interests, on the other [4]. Recommendation no. 10/2000 of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe defines the conflict of interests as being the situation in which the official has a private interest that influences or is capable of influencing the exercise of his public duties impartially and objectively" [5].

Researchers Michael Davis and Andrew Stark define conflict of interest as being a set of circumstances where there is a risk that professional reasoning or actions related to a primary interest will be influenced by a secondary interest [6, p.24]. In accordance with the definitions listed above, we will establish some characteristics of the conflict of interest in the journalistic activity:

- the existence of certain concordances and overlaps of the journalist's personal interests and his professional interests;
- lack of transparency through non-disclosure of the coincidence of personal interests with professional ones;
- obtaining material/other advantages/benefits by maintaining personal interests in agreement with the professional ones;
- establishing relationships outside the material advantages, but capable of influencing public opinion, to detriment of correct information.

L.Ştefan includes the following types of conflicts of interest in the *Practical guide for conflicts of interests and incompatibilities*:

- potential conflict of interest: it is possible that a decision that may be taken could involve a future conflict of interest;

- current conflict of interest: must be taken a decision which involves a conflict of interest at the moment;

- consumed conflict of interests: a decision was taken that served an interest contrary to the public interest, to the client's one or to the company's [7].

In the Republic of Moldova discussions in the public space with the media involvement and the civil society's with the reference to potential or consumed conflicts of interest have emerged only in recent years, with the increasing danger of the press monopolization by politicians, political groups and state officials. The application of legal provisions and, in particular, of sanctions on the press, which admits conflicts of interest in the journalistic activity is still not so obvious, stating that the national legislation does not include norms regarding journalists or media organizations. The existing provisions are of an ethical nature, included in guides of good media practices, codes of ethics, recommendations, etc.

Thus, within the practical guide *Conflict of interests in the activity of journalists* offers some recommendations, in order to avoid creating conflict situations of interest in the activity of journalists. Here are some of them:

- the journalist must stay away from militant political activity, not participate in the election campaign of any party, not go as a participant in the public meetings organized by political parties and must not publicly display promotional signs or materials (badges, logos, posters) of any political formation;

- the journalist must refrain from being part of the management structures (boards of directors, management positions) of associations that could be the

object of his journalistic activity. Exceptions are the professional forms of association, such as professional unions or journalists' associations;

- the journalist will never relate issues in which members of his family - blood relatives or by alliance are parts;

- the journalist will not ask for and will never receive money or other useful benefits from third parties, for himself or others, in order to fulfill his editorial obligations. Gifts that exceed, as a value, the costs of symbolic gifts, will be refused or returned;

- if the journalist has to meet with his source at lunch or "for a coffee", it is preferable to be able to propose the place alone, to ensure that he can pay for his consumption alone;

- the journalist will not make trips which costs are paid by other parties than his editorial staff. Even when the sponsor expressly states that it does not condition the movement of a favorable content of the journalistic material, there is a risk that such expectations may exist or that the public perception will work in the journalist's detriment [8].

Moldovan journalism, more than any other field in this country, needs credibility in the eyes of the local public, but also abroad (when materials are taken from the Moldovan media to be read by the media in other countries), to obtain the reputation of the domain in which only the professionals exercise their activity. The presence, the ignorance, as well as promotion of conflicts of interest in the media leads to the fact that the journalist profession is mixed up with the job of a promoter, whose interests do not always coincide with the objective information of the citizen, but rather, with the grinding and polishing the image of those ones who openly or secretly finances the institution or the journalist himself.

Peter Gross, in his well-known work *Media and Democracy in Eastern European Countries*, observes that two aspects of the East-European media are missing: the public-service function of good faith

and journalistic professionalism, a controversial topic, but essential. At the end of the 1990s, mass-media became subordinate to a large number of interests, predominantly political and commercial ones [9, p.177].

In the Republic of Moldova, the conflict of interests in the media practice is associated in the perception of the public with the simple purchase of the journalist's acceptance, by direct money offering, so that he can write, speak, promote and bring to attention all the subjects that it is of financier/sponsor's interest. We should mention that generally this business is carried out, however at the editorial level and not individually, this way all journalists are being in the position of information service providers, a condemnable, humiliating and abominable position in the eyes of journalists from the independent press.

The biggest suspicion of promoting certain conflicts of interest falls on the journalists, specialized in making economically themed materials. "A journalist who writes about companies can be viewed with great suspicion if he or his close friends own businesses in areas related to those he writes about. The suspicion arises as a result of the fact that journalists have privileged access to information about listed companies and can use this information in their own or those of their immediate interests" [1, p.192].

As we have shown above, in order to avoid the occurrence of conflict of interest situations, each editorial unit should carry out a permanent dialogue with the employees of the media institutions, regarding the awareness, anticipation and prevention of conflict of interest situations. The staff of prestigious newspapers in the West, for example, has clearly defined the situations that journalists employed by these institutions should avoid, in order not to be fired. Thus, editorial codes of conduct impose prohibitions on exploiting in the personal interest information obtained as a journalist. The journalist cannot make investments in the field he writes about and cannot be an advisor

to those he writes about (for example, the economic, political, art, etc.) [11].

Also, no New York Times journalist, for example, may have any actions or other financial interests, including a position on the board of directors of a company or industry about he writes or oversees the publication of commonly used materials (the ban is valid for all areas). As for political involvement, New York Times journalists are forbidden to wear the signs of a party, to have speeches in front of assemblies that would give the impression of partisanship (supporters of a candidate, lobby groups, etc.). Also, the journalist cannot campaign or support in any way a candidate, nor can he donate or raise money for a candidate. Such intra-editorial regulations could make employees even more responsible than the codes of ethics valid for all guild members.

The western practice of documented stipulation of the editorial requirements regarding the integrity of the journalist, unfortunately, has not yet been implemented at the editorial level in the Republic of Moldova. About the dangers of conflicts of interest in the individual activity of journalists, Moldovan newsrooms are being discussed in an informal setting, usually when certain suspicions arise about the journalist's level of equidistance, about how the information was obtained, about the diversity of sources consulted in writing the material, about the journalist's personal opinion, sometimes present in the information materials, due to inattention or non-professionalism, etc.

In addition to the dangers of conflict interests in journalism outside newsrooms, Schultz considers that the danger of pressures exercised by media conglomerates on journalists is equally real [12, p.214]. The conflict of interests sustained and promoted in editorial practice means nothing more than an act of moral corruption, first and foremost, and also material, whose participants are those who should condemn such practices at the societal level.

References

1. RADU, R. Deontologia comunicării publice. Iași: Polirom, 2015. 254 p.
2. Legea nr. 16 din 15.02.2008 cu privire la conflictul de interese. Available: <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=342787> (visited 23.07.2018).
3. ROSE-ACKERMAN, S. Corruption and conflicts of interest. Northampton: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2014.
4. Instrumente Anticorupție. Prevenirea conflictelor de interese. Available: <https://www.transparency.org.ro/stiri/newsletter/TIRONewsletter201518.pdf> (visited 23.07.2018).
5. Recomandarea nr. 10/2000 a Comitetului de Miniștri a Consiliului Europei. Available: https://www.cna.md/public/files/legislatie/rec_2000_10_cod_conduita_funct_public.pdf (visited 23.07.2018).
6. DAVIS, M., STARK, A. Conflict of interest in the professions. Oxford: University Press 2001. 368 p.
7. ȘTEFAN, L. Ghid practic pentru conflicte de interese și incompatibilități. Available: <http://sar.org.ro/wp-content/uploads/2011/08/TRAINING-BOOK.pdf> (visited 22.07.2018).
8. Conflictul de interese în activitatea jurnaliștilor. Ghid practic. Available: <http://www.consiliuldepresa.md/upload/ghid-conflictul-de-interese-in-activitatea-jurnalistilorpdf-5adf9777c4430.pdf> (visited 20.07.2018).
9. GROSS, P. Mass-media și democrația în țările Europei de Est. Iași: Polirom, 2004, 243 p.
10. BULICANU, V. Personalizarea politicii în mass-media între „politcorrectness” și populism. În: La Francopolyphonie. Langues. Litterature. Culture et pouvoir. 2010, nr.5. Chișinău: Institutul de Cercetări Filologice și Interculturale, ULIM, p.312–320.
11. Ethical Journalism. A Handbook of Values and Practices for the News and Editorial Departments of New York Times. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/editorial-standards/ethical-journalism.html> (visited 21.07.2018).
12. SCHULTZ, B. Sports Media: Reporting, Producing and Planning. Burlington: Focal Press, 2013. 230 p.